

ANXIOUS ATTACHMENT STYLE, FEAR OF MISSING OUT AND PHUBBING BEHAVIOR IN ADULTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16530956>

Received
27 March, 2025

Revised
27 June, 2025

Accepted
28 July, 2025

Published
28 July, 2025

ABSTRACT

Fear of Missing Out has become a popular and prominent discussion topic with the widespread and increased use of smart phones, but its relationship to Anxious Attachment and Phubbing Behaviors has not been under the light before. This cross-sectional correlational study was aimed to investigate how Anxious Attachment Style and Phubbing behavior were mediated by Fear of Missing Out in Adults. A total sample of N=304 recruited through the Rule of thumb method using a non-probability convenient sampling approach. Data was gathered using measures of Revised Adult Attachment styles-Close Relationship Version, Fear of Missing Out and General Phubbing Scale. The results show positive correlation in anxious attachment (AA), fear of missing out (FOMO) and Phubbing behavior (PB). Mediation Analysis carried through Hayes process showed significant indirect effect indicating that FOMO was a mediator between AA and PB. The results of present the study suggested that anxious attachment style and fear of missing out play a significant role in determining phubbing behaviors. Results also showed Gender differences in the mean scores of study variables, as AA was more in females, whereas FOMO and PB seen more in males. This study will shed insight on the psychological mechanisms behind PB and FOMO and to improve mental health and well-being, this research can help design therapies that target PB and FOMO in individuals with anxious attachment styles.

Keywords: Anxious Attachment Style, Fear of Missing Out, Phubbing Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

From last few years individual emotional disturbances have been increased which give rise to the factors which contribute in it. Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is a topic that has attracted a lot of attention. FOMO is characterized by two main elements: a) the fear that others are enjoying satisfying and fulfilling moments that one is missing, and b) the steadfast desire to maintain relationships with members of one's social network (Przybylski et

al., 2013). The fulfillment of fundamental psychological needs is necessary for efficient self-regulation, according to the theory of self-determination (Deci & Ryan, 1985). The social contexts that either reinforce or weaken these fundamental psychological needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness are also covered (Deci & Ryan, 2008).

Attachment styles are patterns of emotional and behavioral reactions showed in relationships that have a big effect on psychological and social results such as satisfaction of relationship, well-being and social support (Varley et al., 2024). Bowlby's theory of attachment clarified how attachment types evolve in childhood and impact an adult's social and emotional development. People's early experiences with a caregiver trigger an attachment style that shapes their later non-family relationship foundations (Bowlby, 1973). Phubbing is a negative social behavior that happens when people continue to focus on their phones at the price of paying less attention to the other person, who may feel neglected or ignored (Kaczmarek et al., 2019). In compensating internet usage theory, according to which going online to relieve bad emotions might be prompted by unfavorable life circumstances (Kardefelt-Winther, 2014).

According to the study's findings, phubbing has a major impact on demographic characteristics, FOMO, conformity & addiction of smartphone variables. (Pemayun & Suralaga, 2020). According to a previous study mediation showed the relationship between social appearance anxiety & phubbing was partially mediated by FOMO (Batmaz et al., 2024). Phubbing behavior through the problematic usage of Instagram were both indirectly and directly linked to fear of missing out-state (Balta, 2020). Another study revealed that fear of missing out mediated the association between problematic social networking usage and anxious attachment, which in turn was controlled by life satisfaction (Flack & Boustead, 2021). According to earlier studies, the relationship between social networking which is problematic, its usage and anxious attachment is mediated by the fear of missing out (Liu & Ma, 2019). Previous Study revealed that Insecure attachment styles seem to influence the frequency of phubbing in intimate relationships (Sun & Miller, 2023a).

Significance of Study

In last few years it was seen that Fear of Missing out has become an emerging topic due to Phubbing behavior (ignoring other companion in order to pay attention to phone) I it has significantly increased such has its effect was also seen in the form of social isolation, comparison, need to belong and decline ability to communicate face to face. In this study it was tried to see that how individual attachment styles which are established in any kind of relationship in adults can lead to phubbing due to fear of missing out. Phubbing activity has significantly increased because of the widespread use of cellphones, and it has been connected to a number of detrimental effects, such as social isolation, a reduction in attention span, and a decline in face-to-face communication abilities.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the relationship among Anxious Attachment Style, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults.
2. To explore the mediating role of Fear of Missing Out in the relationship between Anxious Attachment Style and phubbing behavior in adults.
3. To see gender difference in Anxious Attachment style, fear of missing out and phubbing behavior in Adults.

Hypotheses

1. There would significant positive relationships between Anxious Attachment Styles, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults.
2. Fear of missing out would be a significant mediator in the relationship between Anxious Attachment styles and Phubbing behavior in adults.
3. There would be significant gender difference in the mean score of Anxious Attachment styles, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of Attachment Styles, Fear of Missing Out & Phubbing Behavior

Fear of Missing Out as the mediator in relationship between Anxious Attachment Style and Phubbing Behavior

Methodology

A cross-sectional correlational design was used to conduct the present investigation. A total sample of $n=304$, (Male =152, Female=152) was recruited through convenient sampling. The study participants taken from universities from Faisalabad city. Students who used Android cell phones, and were enrolled in any educational programs at any University in Faisalabad were included in the study. College student and the students having any mental or physical disability were not included in the study.

Measures

Personal Information form

A separate demographic information form was developed for this study to collect personal information regarding gender, marital status, residence, and parents.

Revised Adult Attachment scale- Close Relationship Version

Revised Adult Attachment Scale based on 18-item (AAS-R- Close Relationship version) developed by (Collin, 1996). It assesses elements of adult attachment style, such as anxiety about rejection or dislike (Anxiety subscale), comfort with closeness & intimacy (Close subscale), and ease with depending on others (Depend subscale). A 5-point Likert rating system is used for each item, with "1" denoting not at all characteristics and "5" represents very characteristics. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for Close is .81 that shows higher reliability Depend .78 show good reliability and Anxiety .85 which also shows higher reliability respectively. The Close subscale items are 1, 6, 8, 12, 13, and 17. Depend Subscales items include 2, 5, 7, 14, 16, and 18. The Anxiety Subscales has the following items: 3, 4, 9, 10, 11, and 15. 2, 7, 8, 13, 16, 17, and 18 are the scale's reversed items (Collin, 1996).

Fear of Missing Out

The ten-item, one-factor Fear of Missing Out scale (FOMO) was created by Przybylski (Przybylski et al., 2013). For example, "I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me." A score ranging from at least 10 to as much as 50 is obtained by rating each item on a five-point Likert scale that goes from Not at all true (1) to Extremely true (5). Participating students who score higher overall on the Fear of Missing Out are likely to experience higher levels of FOMO. With a high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.81$), test-retest reliability coefficient ($\alpha = 0.81$), and strong psychometric qualities, the FOMO is a good tool (Przybylski et al., 2013).

Phubbing Scale

Phubbing Scale developed by (Karadağ et al., 2015). A measure of phubbing behavior that consists of 10 items that are divided into two categories: (a) communication disruption (5 things, such as "I'm busy with my mobile phone when I'm with friends") and (b) phone fixation (5 items, such as "My phone is always within my reach"). evaluated using a Likert scale with five points, from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The range of the scale's lowest and maximum possible scores is between 10 and 50. People who score 40 or above on the scale indicate that they are addicted to phubbing. Communication disruption, phone preoccupation, and overall scale all had reliability analysis results of =0.87, =0.85, and =0.88 respectively. These Cronbach Alpha show good scale reliability (Karadag et al., 2015).

Results

304 participants were recruited for the present study, with 50 % ($n=152$) were male and 50% ($n=152$) were female. 29 % ($n=89$) were living in hostels and 71% ($n=215$) were Day Scholars. The majority of the sample (92%) were single, and 8 % were married.

Table 1

Correlation between Anxious Attachment Style, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults ($n=304$)

Variables	N	M	SD	1	2	3
1 Anxious Attachment	304	12.06	5.56	-		
2 Fear of Missing Out	304	30.44	8.23	.14*	-	
3 Phubbing Behavior	304	31.52	7.83	.12*	.61**	-

Table 1 revealed that AA has significant correlation with Fear of Missing Out ($r=.14^*, p<.05$) and Phubbing Behavior ($r=.12^*, p<.05$). The Fear of

Missing Out has significant correlation with Phubbing Behavior ($r=.61^{**}, p<.01$).

Table 2

Gender wise Comparison on the mean scores of Study Variables (n=304)

Variables	Female		Male		df	t	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD				
Anxious Attachment	12.89	5.32	11.22	5.68	302	2.65	.00	.30
Fear of Missing Out	27.67	7.67	33.22	7.89	302	-6.22	.00	.71
Phubbing Behavior	28.52	7.03	34.52	7.44	302	-7.21	.00	.82

Table 2 revealed that the significant gender difference on Anxious Attachment Style with $t(302) = 2.65, p <.05$. Findings showed that Female ($M=12.89, SD=5.32$) scores higher than Male ($M=11.22, SD=5.68$). The value of Cohen's d was .30 (<.50) which indicates small size effect. Gender difference on Fear of Missing Out with $t(302) = -6.22, p <.05$. Findings suggest that males ($M=33.22,$

$SD=7.89$) scores higher than Females ($M=27.67, SD= 7.67$). The value of Cohen's d was .71(<.50) which indicates large effect size. Gender difference on Phubbing Behavior with $t(302) = -7.21, p >.05$. Findings suggest that males ($M=34.52, SD=7.44$) scores higher than females ($M=28.52, SD= 7.03$). The value of Cohen's d was .83 (>.50) which indicates larger effect size.

Table 3

Mediation Analysis: Fear of Missing Out serve as mediator in the relationship between Anxious Attachment Style, and Phubbing behavior in adults (n= 304)

	Estimate	SE	p	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Total Effect	.18	.08	.03	.02	.34
Direct effect					
AA → FOMO	.21	.08	.01	.04	.37
FOMO → PB	.58	.04	< .00	.49	.67
AAS → FOMO → PB	.06	.06	.35	-.07	.18
Indirect Effect	.12	.05		.02	.22

Based on 5000 bootstraps samples

Note: Anxious Attachment Style (AAS), Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), Phubbing Behavior (PB) Mediation analysis using the PROCESS SPSS macro (Model 4; Hayes, 2022), was conducted using ordinary least square path analysis, to test whether Fear of Missing Out mediates the link between Anxious Attachment and Phubbing Behavior. The estimates of direct and indirect effects were analyzed, a bootstrapped sample of 5000 was carried out to calculate the indirect effect.

The results showed that Anxious Attachment predicted Fear of Missing Out (direct effect, path "a") $b = .21, p = .01$, and Phubbing behavior was also strongly predicted by FOMO (direct effect, path "b"), $b = .85, p = .001$, suggesting that those with greater attachment anxiety tend to have more FOMO and those with more FOMO, tend to have increased phubbing behavior. Table 3 also

indicating that phubbing behavior did not directly predict by anxious attachment (direct effect, path c) $b = .06, p = .35$, Results indicated that as anxious attachment increased one's vulnerability to FOMO, it necessarily mean increased phubbing behavior, in the absence of other psychological mechanisms involved.

The indirect effect of AA on PB through FoMO was significant, $b = .12, 95\% CI [0.02, 0.22]$, showing that FOMO acts as a mediator in the relationship between AA and PB. The total effect of AA on PB was significant, $b = .18, SE = .08, p = .03$, which implies that AA by itself does not affect PB directly but its effect is exerted through FOMO.

These results are in favor of the mediation hypothesis, which proposes that people with greater AA would be more likely to phub because of increased FOMO rather than anxious attachment directly being related to phubbing.

Fig 2: Mediation Model Showing Total and Direct Effects

Total Effect

Discussion

The goal of this study was to investigate the relationship between Anxious Attachment Styles, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults. Anxious Attachment Style playing role as Independent Variable, Fear of Missing Out as Mediator and Phubbing Behavior as Dependent Variable. Conceptual Framework illustrates the complete diagram of this study. The results of this study supported the findings of previous studies.

As per previous studies, Fear of Missing Out linked with Anxious feelings (Milyavskaya et al., 2018). The result of study showed that Insecure styles of Anxious Attachment had a positive correlation with Fear of Missing Out (Rippé et al., 2023). The role of feeling part of one's social group appears to relate to FoMO as well as anxiety attachment. A common theme of individuals with anxiety attachment is the discord between desired closeness of others and actual (Hazan & Shaver, 1990). The findings that social media FoMO is predicted by high levels of attachment anxiety is in line with other research findings (Blackwell et al., 2017). Individuals with Anxious Style of Attachment shows Fear when they are not with their figures who are close to them, they experience Fear of Missing Out (Holte, 2020). The study revealed that anxious preoccupied attachment styles positively correlated with Phubbing Behavior (Sun & Miller, 2023). These studies support our hypothesis that "There will significant positive correlation between Anxious Attachment Styles and Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults"

Fear of Missing Out had positive relationship with Phubbing Behavior (Batmaz et al., 2024). In a past study the investigation of the relationship between FoMO and phubbing behavior revealed a moderately strong and positive association (Lestari

& Suratmini, 2024). In a study showed a significant positive association between fear of missing out, social media addiction and phubbing (Younas et al., 2022). In a study it was revealed that FoMO, internet addiction and self-control play role as the predictor of smartphone addiction, which predicted the extent to which individuals phub (Chotpitayasunondh & Douglas, 2016). In a study of results showed positive association between FoMO and Phubbing (Batmaz et al., 2024). It support our hypothesis that "There will a significant positive relationship between Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults".

The Anxious style of Attachment positively predicts the FoMO, SNS addiction and Online Social Support (Liu & Ma, 2019). Previous studies also showed that Individuals having Anxiety Style of Attachment have worry that their significant figures will not be available for then and they have fear of missing out (Bartholomew & Horowitz, 1991). In a study it was indicated that Attachment Style of Anxiety predicts Fear of Missing Out, with a partial mediated role of Intolerance Uncertainty (Alfasi, 2021). The results of another study indicated that Anxious Attachment Styles were associated with Fear of Missing Out through indirect mindful attitude effect (Perazzini et al., 2023). Our results of Study results showed that Anxious Attachment Style (AAS) strongly predicted Fear of Missing Out (FoMO), and it suggested that those with greater attachment anxiety tend to have more FoMO which supports our hypothesis that "Fear of Missing Out will significantly mediate between Anxious Attachment Style and Phubbing Behavior in adults. In a study showed that men had higher level of social media Fear of Missing Out than women (Beyens et al., 2016). In another study it was also stated that Males reported more Fear of Missing Out than

Females (Alfasi, 2021). Another study showed no gender difference in Anxious Attachment Style, but our study showed that females have more Anxious Attachment Style than males (Liu & Ma, 2019). So, we can state that “There is a significant gender difference in Anxious Attachment Style, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults”.

Conclusion

Anxious Attachment Styles, Fear of Missing Out and Phubbing Behavior in Adults were examined in this cross-sectional correlation study, with an emphasis on FOMO as a mediating factor by using Hay's Process. According to the study's findings, which strongly supported the suggested mediation model, that Fear of Missing Out as a strong mediator in the relationship between anxious attachment and phubbing behavior in adults.

Limitations and Recommendations

Like every other study, this study also has drawbacks, including it is a cross-sectional study, the data was collected as one moment in time. Moreover, this study was using convenient sampling which raises questions on the generalization of findings. The study using self-report measures and assessment through self-report measures may cause limits and biases.

In future research the other determinants of Phubbing Behaviors should be considered such as Inferiority complex, or the role of Birth Order in developing Phubbing Behavior. For understanding this complex relationship, the future research should use the moderator analysis in future studies. In this study the Phubbing Behavior seen as whole, in future research the dimensions of Phubbing Behavior can be used to see that how they associate with other variables.

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